

Research Paper

Increasing grid access capacity for renewable integration through a grid-forming E-STATCOM under Spanish regulation

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ABSTRACT

The increasing penetration of non-synchronous renewable generation poses significant challenges for grid stability and access capacity, particularly under regulatory frameworks with strict technical requirements. In Spain, rotating synchronous condensers (RSCs) have recently been proposed to strengthen the grid and facilitate renewable integration; however, their deployment is currently restricted by the Transmission System Operator (TSO) due to concerns such as exceeding the permissible short-circuit current levels and the risk of sub-synchronous torsional interactions (SSTI). This paper proposes an energy storage static synchronous compensator (E-STATCOM) model with grid forming (GFM) control as an effective alternative to RSCs for increasing grid access capacity for renewable integration. A control strategy based on the emulation of the synchronous machine swing equation, combined with a power system stabilizer (PSS), is proposed to ensure system stability. The PSS addresses the oscillatory response that arises when emulating the behavior of an RSC in the converter. The concept is validated through simulation studies in PSCAD, using the equivalent electrical network of the Peninsular Electricity System and the Interconnected European System, as specified by current Spanish regulations. Results demonstrate the ability of the proposed E-STATCOM to replicate the key functionalities of RSCs, including inertial response and dynamic voltage support in weak grids, while also meeting fault ride-through (FRT) requirements and ensuring power oscillation damping. It is shown that the proposed solution based on an E-STATCOM with GFM control can be valid for increasing renewable hosting capacity while mitigating the technical and economic drawbacks associated with RSCs.

1. Introduction

In response to the global commitment to decarbonization, the current energy framework is undergoing a deep transformation, with a shift in power generation technologies towards renewable energy sources (RES). In the specific case of Spain, this transition is driven by the planning and objectives outlined in the Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC, for its Spanish acronym) [1], which establishes the foundation for the Electricity Transmission System Development Plan [2], devised by the Spanish Transmission System Operator (TSO). Consequently, this transition is reflected in the current power system planning for the 2026 horizon [2], where wind and photovoltaic generation are expected to account for over 50 % of the installed capacity and the total generation balance on the Iberian Peninsula. The prevailing regulatory framework is therefore oriented towards the

maximization of RES integration. Nevertheless, access capacity to the transmission system and to distribution networks constitutes nowadays a limiting constraint for the deployment of new renewable generation projects. This limitation can be attributed to various factors, including the allocation of access capacity through tendering procedures, the substantial volume already assigned to installations with approved access and connection permits, and the characteristics of the criteria applied in its calculation. Despite the strict requirements enforced, the widespread blackout that occurred in the Iberian Peninsula power system on April 28, 2025, highlights the need to strengthen grid stability.

The Spanish regulatory framework considers both static and dynamic criteria in the determination of access capacity [3]. In the specific case of generation interfaced via power electronics, such as renewable sources, an additional criterion based on short-circuit power is employed to assess grid strength. Currently, the Spanish guidelines

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consider the integration of rotating synchronous condensers (RSCs) to increase grid strength at nodes with insufficient short-circuit power [3]. Rotating synchronous condensers have been traditionally integrated to provide grid support services, such as dynamic reactive power control, inertia provision and short circuit power contribution. However, these machines also present several drawbacks, including the potential to exceed the system's permissible short-circuit current levels and the risk of torsional oscillations. These concerns have led the Spanish TSO to impose certain restrictions on their implementation as a means to increase the access capacity for renewable generation [4]. Furthermore, rotating synchronous condensers exhibit fixed inertia, and their economic impact is significant in terms of investment, installation, maintenance and operational costs, as well as lead time [5].

In this context, the E-STATCOM concept has emerged as a promising alternative [6]. An E-STATCOM combines the reactive power support capabilities of a traditional static synchronous compensator (STATCOM) with the additional ability to supply active power for a limited period of time [7], thereby contributing to system inertia and providing frequency support [8]. This is achieved through the integration and dynamic control of an energy storage system (ESS) on the DC side, which may consist of batteries [9], supercapacitors [8], or a hybrid configuration [10].

Recent research has focused on the application of E-STATCOMs to address power quality issues [11], such as damping power oscillations [12] and smoothing power fluctuations caused by the inherent intermittency of RES [7,13]. Other contributions have advanced the development of control strategies and modeling approaches for their integration into power system studies [14,15]. Regarding the converter topology, many studies refer to Modular Multilevel Converters (MMCs) [8,14,16,17] as the ideal solution for E-STATCOMs, as they enable higher power ratings in a single converter and offer favorable characteristics such as high efficiency, modularity, reduced losses, improved harmonic profile, and fault-tolerant capability.

Several projects around the world are focused on the deployment of E-STATCOMs to provide inertial response and dynamic reactive power support, aiming to address stability challenges in converter-dominated power systems. In Germany, the TSOs identified the need for E-STATCOMs as early as 2020. Since then, a standardized specification for their implementation has been developed [18], and a pilot project has commissioned a 300 MVar E-STATCOM to gain operational experience with this technology [19]. Similar initiatives can be found in Spain, Australia, and Hawaii [15]. Additionally, leading manufacturers have released technical specifications for their commercial implementations—Hitachi refers to the solution as SVC Light® Enhanced [20], while Siemens offers it under the name SVC PLUS FS® [21].

In order to deliver functionalities comparable to those of RSCs, the converter associated with the E-STATCOM must operate under a control strategy known as grid forming (GFM) [8,22]. This type of control enables the converter to behave as a voltage source behind an impedance [23–28]. As a result, the internal voltage phasor remains constant in the transient time frame, inherently responding to disturbances in grid phase or frequency in a manner analogous to synchronous machines.

To achieve this behavior, various control strategies have been proposed in the technical literature, typically classified into three main categories: (1) droop control, (2) synchronous-machine-based methods, and (3) alternative control methodologies [23]. The second category aims to replicate the inertial and damping characteristics of synchronous machines. Among these, one of the most widely adopted approaches involves emulating the swing equation that governs the dynamic response of such devices [29]. However, when this control strategy is configured to make the E-STATCOM behave analogously to an RSC the damping coefficient is set to zero, so in steady state the converter does not supply active power in response to frequency deviations. However, the stability analysis shows that implementing a swing-equation-based control with zero damping leads to an oscillatory response, which is incompatible with the secure and efficient operation of a power system.

To overcome this limitation, the approach proposed in this paper integrates a power system stabilizer (PSS) into the synchronization loop. The PSS is implemented as a washout filter with appropriately tuned gain and time constants and serves to damp the oscillatory dynamics resulting from the zero-damping coefficient in the synchronization loop, thus ensuring a stable response under dynamic conditions.

Within this context, the main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- A comprehensive analysis of the Spanish regulatory framework, focusing on the challenges related to grid access capacity for RES and the limitations arising from the integration of RSCs as a means to increase such capacity.
- The proposal of an E-STATCOM, consisting of an ESS interfaced through a GFM converter, as an alternative solution to increase renewable energy penetration. The concept is justified by demonstrating that, similar to RSCs, the E-STATCOM enhances grid strength by providing dynamic voltage support, inertial response, and power oscillation damping, while also meeting low-voltage ride-through (LVRT) requirements.
- The integration of a PSS into the synchronization loop of the converter to address the oscillatory behavior resulting from the application of a swing-equation-based control with zero damping coefficient, which is required to emulate the steady-state behavior of an RSC.
- The validation of the proposed solution through a series of simulation studies carried out in PSCAD, using the equivalent electrical network of the Peninsular Electricity System and the Interconnected European System for simulation, as defined in the Technical Standard for Monitoring the Compliance of Power-Generating Modules according to EU Regulation 2016/631, applicable to the electrical system of peninsular territory (TS, NTS for its acronym in Spanish) [30]. A comparative analysis is performed between the dynamic response of the proposed E-STATCOM and that of a conventional RSC.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: [Section 2](#) outlines the Spanish regulatory framework for determining grid access capacity, with particular emphasis on the role and limitations of integrating RSCs. [Section 3](#) analyzes the need for strong grids to ensure stable operation in power systems characterized by high shares of RES and introduces the GFM converter as a viable solution. [Section 4](#) delves into the technical capabilities of GFM-based E-STATCOMs to deliver essential grid support services comparable to those provided by RSCs. [Section 5](#) presents the simulation study carried out in PSCAD, including a comparative analysis of the dynamic performance of the proposed E-STATCOM and a conventional RSC. Finally, [Section 6](#) summarizes the main conclusions of the work.

2. Access capacity within the Spanish regulatory framework

In the Spanish regulatory framework, the criteria and methodology for determining the access capacity to the transmission system for generation or storage facilities are defined in [3]. This resolution defines the access capacity of a transmission system node or zone as the maximum active power that can be simultaneously injected at that node or at a set of nodes within the same zone, while ensuring compliance with the criteria established by the applicable regulations. These criteria include technical aspects related to safety, reliability, power quality, sustainability and economic efficiency of the power system. This definition also applies to distribution system nodes that have a significant impact on the transmission system node.

The regulations stipulate that the access capacity determines the limit for granting access authorizations to generation facilities connecting to the transmission system at that node or zone and the acceptability of generation facilities connecting to the underlying

distribution system.

The determination of the access capacity for generation in the transmission system, carried out by the Spanish TSO, considers various types of studies: access capacity based on short-circuit power criteria, access capacity based on static performance and access capacity based on dynamic performance.

European Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/631 of 14 April 2016 establishing a network code on requirements for grid connection of generators [31] categorizes the power-generating modules (PGMs) into synchronous power-generating modules (SPGMs) and power park modules (PPMs). PPMs are defined as generating units connected non-synchronously or through power electronics to the grid.

According to [3], for the determination of the access capacity for PPMs, all three criteria are applied: short-circuit power, static performance, and dynamic performance. In contrast, for the determination of the access capacity for SPGMs only the latter two criteria are applicable.

The access capacity of a node or zone, for each type of generation—PPM or SPGM—is determined as the minimum value resulting from the applicable criteria in each case. Then, the available access capacity margin for each type of generation can be calculated as the difference between the resulting generation access capacity and the capacity associated with generation currently in operation or with valid access and connection permits.

2.1. Access capacity to the transmission grid based on the short-circuit power criterion

2.1.1. Short-circuit power: relationship with grid strength at a node for the connection of a PPM

PPMs primarily refer to wind and photovoltaic power generation plants connected to the grid through power electronics converters. Currently, this technology is predominantly based on power converters equipped with a control system known as grid following (GFL) [2,32].

Through this control scheme, the converter operates similarly to a controllable current source, and the active and reactive power exchange is highly influenced by the performance of the phase-locked loop (PLL). However, PLLs require a sufficiently strong grid to perform correctly, ensuring that fluctuations in system state variables—both under normal conditions and during disturbances—remain within acceptable limits. Excessive variations could lead to PLL malfunction, resulting in delays in the control loop and potential instability in current injection [33,34]. Indeed, recent studies have been investigating control strategies that eliminate the need for PLLs [35].

The integration of non-synchronous generation affects system inertia, short-circuit power, and dynamic voltage control. Therefore, it is essential to establish technical criteria that allow for evaluating the strength of the connection point to ensure the proper operation of PPMs and to prevent interaction phenomena such as voltage and/or frequency instabilities, control interactions, or resonance issues between machines [36].

The strength of a node can be defined as its ability to maintain and control voltage under both steady-state conditions and disturbances [37]. In this context, it can be associated with the extent to which the voltage magnitude and angle at the terminals of a non-synchronous generator remain unaffected by its current injections.

The short-circuit power at a node is a direct indicator of system strength, as it affects:

- Voltage recovery: Ensuring a rapid voltage restoration after fault clearance, preventing the loss of synchronism in SGs.
- Voltage stability: Mitigating voltage instabilities, as low short-circuit power systems are more sensitive to small variations in reactive power injection.
- Power electronic operation: Enabling the stable operation of power electronic equipment, preventing instabilities that could propagate throughout the system.

- Power quality: Maintaining power quality indices, as disturbances introduced by power electronics-based equipment, such as harmonics, have a greater impact in low short-circuit power systems.
- Protection scheme reliability: Ensuring the correct operation of protection systems, facilitating fault isolation, and preventing the loss of synchronism in synchronous generators (SGs) after fault clearance.

Traditionally, the concept of short-circuit power has been used to refer to the strength of a power system. However, other approaches emphasize voltage stiffness with respect to variations in the injected current. Therefore, this concept is associated with the system impedance, meaning that strong and weak grids—typically related to high and low short-circuit power, respectively—can also be understood in terms of low and high grid connection impedance [37].

2.1.2. Access capacity to the transmission system based on the short-circuit power criterion: determination according to current Spanish regulations

Since PPMs rely on GFL power converters, short-circuit power is considered one of the key factors for determining the access capacity. In the Spanish regulatory framework, before the implementation of the current regulations, this criterion was evaluated considering only the short-circuit ratio of the node (SCR_i) [38], defined as:

$$SCR_i = \frac{SCC_i}{P_{PPM_i}} \quad (1)$$

where SCC_i [MVA] is the short-circuit power at the connection node and P_{PPM_i} [MW] denotes the rated power of the PPM. For non-dispatchable generation, [38] established that the generation capacity of an installation or a set of installations sharing a connection point could not exceed 1/20 of the short-circuit power at that point. Consequently, the condition $SCR_i > 20$ had to be met.

Although the SCR index has been widely used to evaluate the strength of a power system for connecting wind farms and HVDC links, it is a purely nodal metric, neglecting the influence of other PPMs connected at electrically proximate nodes.

Furthermore, the threshold of 1/20 (i.e., $SCR_i > 20$), which was established with the objective of achieving a uniform distribution of renewable generation facilities, does not accurately reflect the actual technical capabilities of modern renewable technologies in terms of operational performance, evacuation and integration.

Some technical literature [36,39] suggests that a system with an SCR index greater than 5 can be considered sufficiently strong to ensure the stable operation of GFL converters. In contrast, an SCR index below 3 would indicate a very weak system, where converter instability under system disturbances becomes a critical issue. For SCR values between 3 and 5, rigorous modeling and simulation would be required to accurately assess the behavior of GFL PPMs.

Considering the limitations of the SCR index and the outdated threshold of $SCR_i > 20$, current Spanish regulations provide updated guidelines for considering short-circuit power as a key criterion for assessing grid strength in the context of PPMs integration, thereby ensuring system reliability and supply security. Consequently, the current regulatory framework [3] adopts the weighted short-circuit ratio ($WSCR$), defined as follows:

$$WSCR = \frac{\sum_i^N SCC_i P_{PPM_i}}{(\sum_i^N P_{PPM_i})^2} \quad (2)$$

where SCC_i [MVA] is the effective three-phase short-circuit power at node i within a given electrical influence zone (EIZ), N is the number of nodes within the EIZ and P_{PPM_i} [MW] is the maximum capacity of the PPMs connected or authorized to connect at node i within the EIZ.

This index takes into account the EIZs, which are defined as groups of electrically proximate nodes in which a voltage variation at one node

induces significant voltage changes in the others.

To determine these EIZs, the multi-feed interaction factor (*MIIF*) is employed, defined as:

$$MIIF = \frac{\Delta V_j}{\Delta V_i} \quad (3)$$

where ΔV_i is the voltage change at node i [kV or p.u.] and ΔV_j is the voltage change at node j due to the voltage variation at node i [kV or p.u.]. For nodes i and j to be considered part of the same EIZ, the *MIIF* index (evaluated in steady-state load flow analysis) for either node must be equal to or greater than 0.98.

A weaker system will yield larger EIZs due to a reduced capacity to dynamically control voltage magnitude and angle (primarily provided by synchronous generation), meaning that voltage variations at one node may influence a larger number of nodes [2].

Finally, current regulations [3] state that the access capacity (in MW) of node j is given by:

$$\text{Access Capacity of Node } j = \frac{S_{ccj}}{WSCR} \frac{\sum_i^N S_{cc_i}^2}{(\sum_i^N S_{cc_i})^2} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the access capacity of the nodes within an EIZ is allocated based on their respective short-circuit power values.

2.1.3. Integration of a rotating synchronous condenser to increase the PPM access margin: determination and limitations according to current Spanish regulations

The calculation of the *WSCR* index, as defined in (2), considers the effective three-phase short-circuit power as the power supplied by the elements that enhance system strength. Specifically, [3] accounts exclusively for the short-circuit current contribution of SGs. Therefore, the *S_{cc}* at a given node is primarily determined by the number of electrically proximate SGs, as well as by the meshing of the transmission system.

Current regulations [3] allow for the incorporation of RSCs at PPMs seeking connection to the transmission system. RSCs provide dynamic system voltage control and exhibit behavior similar to SGs in terms of inertia provision and short-circuit power contribution during disturbances or fault conditions. This capability can be further enhanced by incorporating a flywheel. The additional short-circuit power contribution provided by RSCs is the characteristic that the Spanish TSO takes into account for the modification of the access capacity for PPMs considering the *WSCR* criterion. According to the TSO, the additional capacity can be estimated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Additional PPM Capacity (MW)} &= \frac{S_{ccRSC}}{WSCR_{\text{threshold}_{\text{node}}}} \\ &= \frac{S_{RSC} \left(\frac{1}{X_{RSC}'' + X_t} \frac{S_{RSC}}{S_t} + X_t \frac{S_{RSC}}{100} \right)}{WSCR_{\text{threshold}_{\text{node}}}} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where S_{ccRSC} [MVA] is the short-circuit power contribution of the RSC, S_{RSC} [MVA] is the apparent power of the RSC, X_{RSC}'' [p.u. on SRC base] is the subtransient reactance of the RSC, X_t [p.u. on transformer base] is the transformer reactance, S_t [MVA] is the apparent power of the transformer and X_l [p.u. on 100 MVA base] is the reactance of the connection circuit. This expression determines the short-circuit power contribution of the RSC based on its representation as a voltage source behind a series impedance. The *WSCR* threshold for each node is publicly available information provided by the Spanish TSO.

Prior to current regulations, which came into effect in 2024, the previous standards from 2021 [40] had already considered the possibility of incorporating RSCs to increase the PPM access capacity without specific limitations. However, three years after the implementation of

[40], it became necessary to reassess this aspect, as it was observed that, under certain circumstances, the incorporation of RSCs could impact system security. This was primarily due to the risk of exceeding the maximum permissible short-circuit current values in the node or area, or the potential for interactions with other equipment that could lead to subsynchronous torsional interaction (SSTI) [3,4].

On the one hand, RSCs naturally inject short-circuit currents that can be several times higher than the nominal value, which could be beneficial for fault detection, protection system operation, and ensuring reliable fault clearing by conventional protection devices. However, it is essential to ensure that the expected short-circuit currents within the system are acceptable and that the circuit breakers are capable of interrupting them. Exceeding the maximum permissible current can lead to damage in power system components, such as circuit breakers and transformers, reducing their effectiveness and lifespan.

On the other hand, the installation of RSCs can give rise to SSTI, a phenomenon that causes instability in synchronous machines. This phenomenon affects both the electrical and mechanical modes of the system at frequencies below the synchronous frequency, potentially leading to interactions with equipment and causing energy exchanges between the machine and the grid at these frequencies. Consequently, SSTI can result in mechanical and active power oscillations that may damage the RSCs themselves, as well as other elements of the power system [4].

Consequently, under the current regulatory framework [3], the Spanish TSO is required to publish the nodes where the available access capacity is either limited or nullified for RSC integration due to these two phenomena. These limitations, explicitly delineated in the Spanish regulations, present an opportunity to contemplate the alternative configuration proposed in this paper: an ESS operating in conjunction with a GFM converter, functioning as an E-STATCOM. As demonstrated in this work, this configuration offers a set of technical capabilities that enhance grid strength while mitigating the issues associated with RSCs.

3. Need for strong grids in the operation of PPMs

3.1. The role of GFL converters in current PPMs

The predominance of wind and photovoltaic plants utilizing GFL electronic converters in PPMs justifies the need for a criterion to assess grid strength. Current regulations use the short-circuit power criterion to determine the access capacity of these power-generating modules.

The operating principle of GFL converters is based on tracking grid voltages [41] and injecting a current with a specific angle phase over the voltage. [23]. Their control is typically implemented in a rotating *dq* reference frame, whose orientation relative to a fixed reference system must be aligned with the grid voltage vector [24]. To achieve this, the PLL estimates the magnitude and phase of the grid voltage at the network connection (NCP) [32]. The control system then adjusts the converter terminal voltage to ensure that the *dq*-axis currents—and consequently, the active and reactive power injections—adhere to the specified setpoints [23].

GFL converters, therefore, behave as current sources controlled by voltage. Consequently, they do not inherently exhibit voltage source behavior, unlike SGs [32], which have traditionally been responsible for maintaining system voltage and frequency, as well as providing ancillary services for system stability and security.

The performance of GFL converters ultimately depends on the accurate measurement and estimation of grid voltage. Consequently, a relatively stable voltage at the measurement point is required, as these converters may experience malfunctions in weak grids [42], especially during disturbances [23]. Furthermore, in their standard configuration within photovoltaic and wind power plants, GFL converters are not generally designed with sufficient energy storage capacity to emulate an inertial response, unless they are operated below their maximum power operating point [43]. If sufficient energy is available at the DC terminals,

the contribution of GFL converters to frequency-power regulation relies on a measurement-based process known as fast frequency response (FFR). This approach determines the necessary active power contribution based on frequency deviation measurements and adjusts the power output accordingly. However, this response is not instantaneous [44] and involves a delay due to frequency estimation, meaning that these converters do not provide a true inertial response. Additionally, GFL converters cannot operate in islanded mode and therefore cannot contribute to system restoration in the event of a blackout [45].

3.2. GFM converters for increasing access capacity margins for PPMs in high renewable penetration scenarios

As discussed in the previous section, GFL converters alone are insufficient to provide all the essential services and technical capabilities required for the stable and secure operation of the power system, both under normal operating conditions and during faults and disturbances [46]. Traditionally, these functions have been covered by SGs, considering their role as voltage sources and the inherent availability of stored kinetic energy in their rotating masses. Currently, the growing penetration of non-synchronous renewable generation displacing SGs has driven the development of solutions that can provide functions analogous to those of SGs. In the context of access capacity, such solutions would enable an increase in access capacity margins for PPMs without compromising system stability.

The integration of RSCs is an alternative already being considered in the energy sector and incorporated into the actual Spanish regulatory framework [3]. However, this technology presents several drawbacks explicitly recognized in the national regulations as outlined in section 2.1.3 [3]. Additionally, the inertia of RSCs remains fixed once installed. These challenges generate potential for the implementation of energy storage systems that operate with a GFM converter as a static synchronous compensator (E-STATCOM) [5]. This solution offers significantly greater flexibility compared to RSCs, as it allows for the adjustment of the inertial response through control strategies. Additionally, in the event of a fault, the short-circuit current provided by these devices is limited to protect the electronic components. This addresses the restriction of exceeding admissible currents, and through control techniques, their response can be modified to prevent interactions with other elements, thus reducing the risk of undesirable oscillations.

Additionally, GFM converters act as voltage sources and are suitable for operating in weak grids (in relation to the S_{cc} provided by synchronous generation) [23]. Therefore, GFM converters can accommodate a larger number of GFL PPMs by contributing to system stability and providing nearly all the services traditionally provided by SGs [46].

GFM converters have demonstrated their ability to enhance grid strength in high renewable penetration scenarios. Notable examples of their implementation include projects in Australia (Dalrymple Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), Hornsdale BESS - Tesla), the United Kingdom (Dersalloch Windfarm - National Grid UK, Scottish Power Renewables), and the United States (various projects led by General Electric) [23]. Studies in [25] highlight that as grid strength decreases due to the reduced presence of synchronous generation, GFL converters may experience instability issues. Although advances in GFL control strategies have enabled their operation in increasingly weaker grids, these improvements remain inherently limited. In power systems with high penetration of converter-based generation, GFM converters become essential for maintaining voltage and frequency stability, thereby ensuring overall grid reliability. In the international context of grid codes, the National Grid Electricity System Operator (NESO) of the United Kingdom, explores in [26] the use of GFM converters as an alternative to RSCs to address grid stability issues in scenarios where synchronous generation is displaced by renewable generation. This document is particularly relevant as it provides the most advanced technical requirements for GFM converters.

The current Spanish regulatory framework explicitly acknowledges

the potential for GFM technology to receive special consideration in the application of the short-circuit power criterion for determining the access capacity of PPMs [3]. However, the regulations currently in force have not yet developed specific provisions for this, highlighting the need to establish national guidelines to define the applicable technical requirements.

4. Technical capabilities of GFM converters as static synchronous condensers

This section presents the key technical capabilities of a GFM converter combined with an ESS, operating as an E-STATCOM. When integrated with a PPM, this configuration can function similarly to an RSC, contributing to grid strength at the designated node and thereby increasing access capacity.

4.1. Fundamental characteristics

GFM converters impose the voltage phasor at the control point using a control system which is designed to dynamically regulate the magnitude and angle of the phasor, enabling synchronization with the grid without estimating the grid voltage angle.

Various control strategies for GFM converters can be found in the technical literature; however, their common objective is to impose a voltage synchronized with the grid, enabling current to flow into it [25]. This controlled voltage-source behavior allows GFM converters to provide system support in a manner similar to SGs. Fig. 1 presents the basic schematic of a GFM converter connected to the grid.

Among the various control architectures that GFM converters can adopt, Fig. 2 illustrates the typical configuration consisting of internal cascaded control loops, with the current control loop and the voltage control loop implemented at the internal level [23,33,47].

The GFM converter operates as a voltage source, defined by its magnitude v^* and phase angle θ . The internal current and voltage control loops use these references to generate the internal voltage reference e , from which the gate signals for the semiconductors $S_1 \dots S_6$ are derived, thereby synthesizing the AC voltage waveform. The control is implemented in a dq reference frame, whose orientation relative to a fixed reference system is determined by θ .

The voltage magnitude reference is obtained either directly when the GFM operates as a PV node or through an external reactive power control loop (RPC) when functioning as a PQ node. On the other hand, the phase angle reference is determined by an external active power control loop (APC) or active power synchronization loop. Various architectures exist for these external control loops; however, many of them are designed to emulate the swing equation of SGs [48].

4.2. Voltage source behavior

Behavior as a controlled voltage source is one of the most significant characteristics of GFM converters. Through their control system, GFM converters must maintain their voltage reference in terms of magnitude, phase and frequency, regardless of the connected loads [27]. Thus, they operate as an internal voltage source, separated from the connection point by a predominantly inductive impedance: the output filter impedance. This behavior can be effectively represented using a Thevenin equivalent circuit [23–28].

Since GFM converters behave as voltage sources, they present a different response to disturbances compared to GFL converters. Their response is significantly more favorable in terms of system stability, particularly in weak grids [23,25,27]. The internal voltage source exhibits limited dynamics in frequency, phase and voltage magnitude, which act as a form of stiffness, constrained by the controller's bandwidth (typically below 5 Hz [26]). In the transient regime—during and immediately after a disturbance—GFM converters behave as a constant voltage source [25]. As a result, any variation in grid voltage magnitude

Fig. 1. Grid-forming E-STATCOMs are proposed to increase renewable energy access capacity.

Fig. 2. Internal current and voltage control loops.

and/or phase instantaneously modifies the voltage drop across the impedance, thereby altering the converter's output current [27].

Considering that the impedance is predominantly inductive, the active power transfer equation at the beginning of the disturbance is given by:

$$P = \frac{EV}{X_f} \sin \delta \quad (6)$$

where P [p.u.] is the active power supplied by the converter, E [p.u.] is the internal voltage of the converter, V [p.u.] is the voltage at the connection point, δ is the phase difference between the internal voltage and the grid voltage, and X_f [p.u.] is the inductance between the internal voltage source and the NCP. According to this equation, any fluctuation in grid phase or frequency results in an instantaneous change (within less than 5 ms [26,28]) in the active power output of the converter, assuming the internal voltage remains unaffected in the transient timeframe [23–27]. The concepts of active power provision in response to phase jumps, as well as the definitions of damping active power and inertial active power are derived from this principle. These are defined in the grid code [26] as essential technical capabilities required for GFM converters to support system stability.

Similarly, the voltage source behavior (considering the dynamics of the internal voltage amplitude) enables the instantaneous provision of reactive current in response to fluctuations in grid voltage magnitude

[27].

4.3. Inertial response

The rotor speed of a SG is synchronized with the frequency of the system. It naturally counteracts any imbalance between generation and demand by the kinetic energy stored in the rotating masses of the generator's rotor and drivetrain. This energy release effectively mitigates rapid frequency fluctuations, thereby reducing the Rate of Change of Frequency (*RoCoF*). This phenomenon, referred to as inertial response [26,48], also applies to RSCs. However, in contrast to SGs, these machines are not coupled to a drivetrain, though they may incorporate a flywheel to enhance inertia.

Equipping GFM converters with an inertial response analogous to that of SGs is essential for enhancing power system stability, particularly in terms of *RoCoF* and frequency deviations. To this end, numerous GFM control architectures have been developed to emulate the inertial characteristics of SGs by synthesizing its swing equation through control. A basic implementation of an active power synchronization loop based on this equation according to:

$$P^* - P = 2H \frac{d\omega_i}{dt} + D(\omega_i - \omega_0) \quad (7)$$

is illustrated in Fig. 3, where P^* [p.u.] is the reference power, P [p.u.] is the active power delivered by the converter at the connection point

Fig. 3. Active power synchronization loop based on the synchronous machine swing equation.

(dependent on the phase angle between the grid voltage and the converter voltage), ω_i [p.u.] is the internal frequency, ω_0 [p.u.] is the nominal frequency, and D and H [s] are the design values for the damping coefficient and the inertia constant. This formulation defines the inertial behavior of the GFM converter through the parameters H and D , which are integrated into the active power synchronization loop in a manner analogous to SGs [23,27,48].

Therefore, a static synchronous compensator based on a GFM converter can provide an inertial response similar to that of an RSC, provided that sufficient energy and power are available on the DC side [23,28]. This is ensured by appropriately sizing the associated energy storage system. However, a key advantage of GFM converters over RSCs is the possibility to adjust parameters H and D to achieve the desired response according to system requirements. Furthermore, these parameters can be dynamically adjusted during operation, providing significantly greater flexibility than RSCs [8,23,48].

The parameter D is selected based on the desired steady-state power-frequency characteristic, considering that the damping coefficient in p.u. is the inverse of the droop constant, K_{droop} :

$$K_{droop} = \frac{1}{D} = -\frac{\Delta\omega}{\Delta P} \quad (8)$$

where ΔP represents the p.u. active power output to a p.u. frequency deviation $\Delta\omega$. Operating analogously as an RSC, participation in frequency regulation services is not considered for the E-STATCOM. Taking this into account, under steady-state conditions, the E-STATCOM does not supply active power in response to a sustained frequency deviation, which also allows for a reduced energy storage capacity requirement. Consequently, the control system is designed with a damping coefficient $D = 0$.

On the other hand, H is determined according to the required inertial response [23,27,48]. For a given p.u. $RoCoF$, the p.u. variation in active power due to the inertial response in steady state, $\Delta P_{inertial}$, is given by:

$$\Delta P_{inertial} = -2H RoCoF \quad (9)$$

indicating that inertial power is proportional to the inertia constant and $RoCoF$ [24,27,48]. Similar to SGs, GFM converters provide nearly constant inertial power for a constant $RoCoF$ under steady-state conditions [27,48].

In summary, the combination of voltage-source behavior, a control strategy that emulates the inertial characteristics of SGs, and a properly dimensioned energy storage system enables GFM converters to deliver a true inertial response [27]. This enhances grid resilience and facilitates the integration of power plants equipped with GFL converters.

4.4. Power oscillation damping

This section provides a justification for the need for a power system stabilizer when the droop coefficient D of the GFM active power synchronization loop is set to zero. Furthermore, it details the design of the proposed PSS control developed in this work to address the resulting stability issues.

The linearized form of (7) around an equilibrium point, expressed in p.u., results in the following expression in the s -domain:

$$\Delta P^* - \Delta P = (Js + D)\Delta\omega_i \quad (10)$$

with $J = 2H$, being J the moment of inertia.

Additionally, the increment $\Delta\delta$ in the angular position deviation of the dq frame rotating at ω_i , with respect to a reference frame rotating at the grid frequency ω_g , expressed as a function of the p.u. increment of the internal frequency, $\Delta\omega_i$, and the grid frequency, $\Delta\omega_g$, is given by:

$$\frac{1}{\omega_0} \frac{d\Delta\delta}{dt} = \Delta\omega_i - \Delta\omega_g \quad (11)$$

with ω_0 expressed in rad/s and being $\Delta\omega_i = (\omega_i - \omega_0)/\omega_0$ and $\Delta\omega_g = (\omega_g - \omega_0)/\omega_0$. Fig. 4 presents the block diagram representing both equations and the dynamic relationship of ΔP and $\Delta\delta$:

Likewise, the linearized form of equation (6) yields to:

$$\Delta P = \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial \delta}\right)_0 \Delta\delta = \left(\frac{V_0 E_0}{X_f}\right) \cos\delta_0 \Delta\delta = K_s \Delta\delta \quad (12)$$

grouping the constants in K_s , defined as the synchronization constant.

According to Fig. 4, the dynamic response of the VSC, given by $\Delta\delta$, depends on variations in the active power reference ΔP^* and the grid frequency $\Delta\omega_g$. By considering equations (10), (11) and (12), the dynamic relationship of $\Delta\delta$ under changes on ΔP^* , assuming a constant grid frequency ($\Delta\omega_g = 0$), can be derived as follows:

$$\frac{\Delta\delta}{\Delta P^*} = \frac{\omega_0}{Js^2 + Ds + \omega_0 K_s} \quad (13)$$

Likewise, the transfer function between $\Delta\delta$ and $\Delta\omega_g$, assuming a constant power reference ($\Delta P^* = 0$), is given by:

$$\frac{\Delta\delta}{\Delta\omega_g} = -\frac{J\omega_0 s}{Js^2 + Ds + \omega_0 K_s} - \frac{D\omega_0}{Js^2 + Ds + \omega_0 K_s} \quad (14)$$

By substituting (12) into the previous equation and noting that $s\Delta\omega_g$ represents the rate of change of frequency, the following relationship is obtained under steady state conditions ($s \rightarrow 0$):

$$\Delta P_{s \rightarrow 0} = -J RoCoF - D\Delta\omega_g = \Delta P_{inertial} + \Delta P_{droop} \quad (15)$$

The first term corresponds to the power injected in steady state due to the inertial response, as presented in (9), while the second corresponds to the steady-state droop response, according to (10).

Based on the previous equations, stability can be analyzed as a function of the parameter D . When $D = 0$ the system exhibits two purely imaginary conjugate poles located at $\pm j\sqrt{\omega_0 K_s/J}$, resulting in an oscillatory (marginally stable) response. For $D > 0$, the system response becomes stable, with different scenarios. If $D^2 > 4J\omega_0 K_s$, the system has two distinct negative real poles, leading to an overdamped response. Conversely, if $D^2 < 4J\omega_0 K_s$, the system has two distinct complex conjugate poles with negative real parts, resulting in an underdamped response. Finally, if $D^2 = 4J\omega_0 K_s$, being $D = D_c$, the system has two equal negative real poles, yielding a critically damped response. Fig. 5 shows the root locus for the case of $H = 6.25$ s and $K_s = 5$ p.u. (calculated at the operating point $E_0 = V_0 = 1$ p.u., $X_f = 0.2$ p.u. and $\cos\delta_0 \sim 1$).

As shown, when the converter is configured as a static synchronous compensator with $D = 0$, providing only the inertial response, distur-

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the linearized APC model.

Fig. 5. Pole loci under variation of D with $H = 6.25$ s, $K_s = 5$ p.u. and $\omega_0 = 100\pi$ rad/s

bances in the grid frequency or variations in the active power reference may lead to an oscillatory system response. To achieve a stable inertial response, a PSS is proposed to be incorporated into the synchronization loop. Fig. 6 presents the proposed PSS integrated into the linearized APC model. The PSS is implemented as a washout filter, where K_w denotes the PSS gain and T_w the time constant. The corresponding transfer function is given by:

$$\frac{\Delta\omega_{PSS}}{\Delta P} = -K_w \left(\frac{T_w s}{T_w s + 1} \right) \quad (16)$$

By substituting $D = 0$ into (14) and expressing it in differential form, the following equation is obtained:

$$J \frac{d^2(\Delta\delta)}{dt^2} + \omega_0 K_s \Delta\delta = -\omega_0 J \frac{d(\Delta\omega_g)}{dt} \quad (17)$$

On the other hand, considering (12) and the relationship between the angle and the frequency, (16) can be expressed in terms of $\Delta\delta$ as follows:

$$T_w \frac{d^2(\Delta\delta)}{dt^2} = -K_w K_s T_w \omega_0 \frac{d(\Delta\delta)}{dt} \quad (18)$$

By adding the last two equations, the following is obtained:

$$[J + T_w] \frac{d^2(\Delta\delta)}{dt^2} + K_w K_s T_w \omega_0 \frac{d(\Delta\delta)}{dt} + \omega_0 K_s \Delta\delta = -\omega_0 J \frac{d(\Delta\omega_g)}{dt} \quad (19)$$

Equation (19) can be expressed as:

$$J' \frac{d^2(\Delta\delta)}{dt^2} + D' \frac{d(\Delta\delta)}{dt} + \omega_0 K_s \Delta\delta = -\omega_0 J \frac{d(\Delta\omega_g)}{dt} \quad (20)$$

defining $J' = J + T_w$ and $D' = K_w K_s T_w \omega_0$. The transfer function between $\Delta\delta$ and $\Delta\omega_g$ in the s -domain expression is therefore:

$$\frac{\Delta\delta}{\Delta\omega_g} = -\frac{\omega_0 J s}{J' s^2 + D' s + \omega_0 K_s} \quad (21)$$

It can be observed that in the case of a null T_w , i.e., in the absence of the PSS, (21) is equivalent to (14), when $D = 0$. The value of J' is primarily determined by the moment of inertia J , as it is typically significantly larger in magnitude than T_w . Once T_w is defined, the gain K_w sets the value of D' , which can then be selected to achieve the desired damping.

Fig. 7 shows that, for a given T_w , when K_w is equal to zero, two purely imaginary conjugate poles are located at $\pm j\sqrt{\omega_0 K_s / J'}$. As this parameter increases, two complex conjugate poles with a negative real part appear, up to a certain value of K_w , denoted as K_{wc} , beyond which two distinct real negative poles are obtained.

This demonstrates that the proposed PSS enables the E-STATCOM to operate as an RCS, effectively addressing the stability issue when the damping coefficient D is set to zero, and ensuring a stable system response. Therefore, another key technical capability to consider when integrating a GFM converter as an E-STATCOM is its contribution to system stability.

Fig. 6. PSS integrated into the APC linearized model.

Fig. 7. Pole loci under variation of K_w with $H = 6.25$ s, $K_s = 5$ p.u., $T_w = 0.5$ p.u. and $\omega_0 = 100\pi$ rad/s.

4.5. Voltage control in weak grids

GFM converters have the capability to dynamically regulate voltage in weak grids, characterized by low short-circuit power and high resistive components ($SCR < 5$ and $X/R < 10$) [23]. These converters enable the implementation of a voltage control loop similar to the automatic voltage regulator (AVR) used in synchronous generators.

Voltage regulation at the connection point is one of the main challenges in weak grid scenarios [23], often necessitating restrictions on the hosting capacity of PGMs under such conditions. To address this issue, the integration of an E-STATCOM, which regulates voltage magnitude at the connection point by injecting or absorbing reactive power through a GFM converter coupled with an ESS—mimicking the behavior of an RSC—emerges as a viable solution. This approach enables effective voltage control at the grid node where a renewable power plant seeks access and connection.

4.6. Fault-ride-through capabilities

GFM converters can comply with fault ride-through (FRT) requirements, which refer to their capability to remain connected during voltage disturbances, such as low-voltage events caused by faults [29], also referred to as LVRT. Consequently, this represents an additional technical capability that can be provided by the E-STATCOM proposed in this paper. This behavior is consistent with their operation as voltage sources, in which the control architecture maintains the internal converter voltage in case of a reduction of the terminal voltage.

In the event of a severe voltage dip at the converter terminals due to a fault, grid codes and standards generally require the converter to inject current up to its rated capacity, typically prioritizing reactive current to support voltage restoration [37,49]. When operating as an E-STATCOM, the active power reference is set to zero, allowing the voltage control loop to increase the reactive current contribution until it reaches its maximum limit.

The control implemented in GFM converters also complies with LVRT requirements in the event of unbalanced voltage dips [49]. GFM converters behave as a real positive-sequence voltage source behind the filter impedance, while maintaining the internal negative-sequence voltage at zero through control. As a result, when a negative-sequence voltage component is present at the converter terminals, the system injects a negative-sequence current.

In relation to the above, another key aspect to consider in the control of a GFM converter is the methodology used for current limitation during disturbances. Several approaches can be found in the literature, generally categorized into the use of saturators in the internal current control loops [50], virtual impedances [51], or switching to a GFL control mode [52].

5. Case study

This section presents a series of simulation cases that assess the effectiveness of the proposed E-STATCOM in enhancing grid strength at the desired node. The E-STATCOM operates in conjunction with a GFL power-generation module at the connection point. By improving grid stiffness at this node, the E-STATCOM can potentially increase its hosting capacity.

Three sets of simulations were conducted to demonstrate that the E-STATCOM:

- Reinforces system inertial response: It contributes to maintaining system frequency within acceptable limits by providing additional inertia without introducing undesirable oscillations.
- Enhances voltage control: It contributes to the stabilization and control of voltage levels at the node.
- Complies with FRT requirements: It remains connected during low-voltage events caused by faults and provides reactive current during the voltage dip to support voltage recovery after the fault is cleared.

The dynamic system used for these simulations is the equivalent electrical network of the Peninsular Electricity System and the Inter-connected European System for simulation, as defined in the Technical Standard for Monitoring the Compliance of Power-Generating Modules according to EU Regulation 2016/631 [30].

Fig. 8 (a) illustrates this system, which consists of an equivalent SPGM, designated as GEN_{EQ} , connected to the node also referred to as GEN_{EQ} . The voltage adaptation between this node and the equivalent node of the electrical system, EQ_{SYSTEM} , is carried out through the equivalent machine transformer, TRF_{EQ} . A representative load (P , Q) must be considered at this node [30]. The power-generation module to be assessed is connected to the grid at the NCP. From this node, the transmission grid is represented by the line EQ_{SYSTEM} -NCP, which connects the NCP to the EQ_{SYSTEM} node [30]. Additionally, Fig. 8(b)-(d) illustrate the system configurations employed for the various simulations performed

The simulations were performed using PSCAD to evaluate the system response to a series of disturbances. The results were compared under different configurations: 1) when only the GFL PPM is connected at the NCP; 2) when a rotating synchronous condenser operates in conjunction with the GFL PPM; 3) when the proposed E-STATCOM, operating in GFM mode, is connected to the node along with the GFL PPM. In addition, some simulations were conducted by varying certain parameters of the E-STATCOM.

5.1. Modeling and implementation in PSCAD

The parameters to be used for the different elements of the equivalent power grid model are specified in the Technical Standard [30]. Some of these parameters must be calculated based on the maximum capacity of the PPM under assessment, the nominal voltage, and the short-circuit power at the NCP. This short-circuit power must be adjusted to ensure that the short-circuit ratio at this node is equal to 5.

In this case study, the equivalent SPGM, GEN_{EQ} , has a power rating of 500 MVA, while the power-generating module under assessment is a 100-MVA PPM connected to the power system through the GFL converter. In the various configurations evaluated, for comparison purposes, both the RSC and the E-STATCOM have an apparent power rating of 30 MVA and an inertia constant, H , of 6.25 s.

The control of the E-STATCOM implemented in the PSCAD simulations follows the general scheme shown in Fig. 1, incorporating the cascaded voltage and current control loops depicted in Fig. 2, with the addition of a current limitation block. Since the damping coefficient is set to $D = 0$, a power system stabilizer is required, as presented in section 4.4. Accordingly, the synchronization loop integrates the PSS proposed

Fig. 8. Equivalent Electric network of the Peninsular Electricity System and the Interconnected European System for simulation, as defined in [30]; a) network layout, b) configuration for assessing the impact of the E-STATCOM on system frequency, c) configuration for voltage control analysis, and d) configuration for evaluating compliance with LVRT requirements.

in this paper, as illustrated in Fig. 9.

Several tables in the Appendix contain the parameters of the components constituting the equivalent power network, as well as the different configurations under study.

Fig. 9. Synchronization loop incorporating the proposed PSS scheme.

5.2. Inertial response for the frequency support

Fig. 8 (b) presents the schematic representation for the first set of simulations. These simulations aim to assess the system response to an increase in active power demand. By introducing a disturbance in the demand, the inertial response of the E-STATCOM can be evaluated and compared with the response of the RSC under the same conditions.

First, the simulations are initialized so that all dynamic state variables are set to the initial values obtained from a load flow study. In the proposed case study, the initial load flow is characterized by a consumption of 360 MW and 0 MVar at the EQ_{SYSTEM} node (P, Q load in the diagram), and an injection of 40 MW and 0 MVar at the PPM node, according to the operating setpoints of the GFL power-generating module. Therefore, the GEN_{EQ} node serves as the balancing node.

In scenarios 2) and 3), the initial reactive power injection by both the RSC and the E-STATCOM is set to the value required for voltage control at their terminals, in accordance with the specified setpoint.

After initializing the simulation, the disturbance occurs at time $t = 5$ s, which consists of an increase of 60 MW in the active power demand at the EQ_{SYSTEM} node, due to the connection of load P_1 (with $Q_1 = 0$ MVar).

Fig. 10 and illustrates the evolution of the system frequency and the RoCoF for the different scenarios analyzed. The E-STATCOM₁ and E-

Fig. 10. Evolution of the system frequency (a) and $RoCoF$ (b) calculated over a 500 ms time, in response to the increase in active power demand.

STATCOM₂ scenarios both correspond to case 3), differing in the PSS parameters used in the converter control, which are provided in the Appendix.

The frequency nadir, which drops to 48.83 Hz in scenario 1), improves when either an RSC or an E-STATCOM is incorporated. Specifically, with the inclusion of the RSC under the defined characteristics, this value increases to 48.91 Hz. By adjusting the PSS parameters, a similar response can be achieved with the E-STATCOM, as observed in the E-STATCOM₁ case, where the nadir reaches 48.92 Hz. Further tuning of these parameters allows for variations in the E-STATCOM response, as demonstrated in the E-STATCOM₂ scenario, where the nadir improves to 48.96 Hz.

Similarly, $RoCoF$ within the first 500-millisecond time window is reduced from -1.173 Hz/s in scenario 1) to -1.056 Hz/s in case 2). For the E-STATCOM, the initial PSS parameterization results in a $RoCoF$ of -1.048 Hz/s, while the second configuration yields -1.11 Hz/s.

In conclusion, although all scenarios exhibit similar responses due to the identical disturbance applied, the inclusion of an RSC enhances dynamic performance. The results from this study show that this

improvement can be matched or even surpassed by the E-STATCOM through adjusting the parameters of its control loops, confirming its suitability as an effective alternative for strengthening system stability.

Fig. 11(a)-(c) present the active power response of the RSC/E-STATCOM, the equivalent SPGM, and the PPM under study, respectively. These responses demonstrate that the observed differences in the frequency trends across the various scenarios are attributable to the transient active power contribution of the RSC and E-STATCOM, in accordance with their inertial response. Despite having a nominal power rating of only 5.55% relative to the equivalent synchronous generator, both the nadir and the $RoCoF$ show an improvement when the E-STATCOM or RSC are incorporated.

Following the disturbance, as illustrated in the responses, the GFM E-STATCOM, in contrast to the GFL PGM, contributes to the mitigation of the frequency drop, in conjunction with the equivalent SPGM. However, it is the latter that ultimately assumes the active power demand increase at the new operating point. In steady-state conditions, the E-STATCOM is designed to supply zero active power, for which the damping factor of its control, D was set to 0, as presented in this paper.

Fig. 11. Evolution of the active power output of different system elements following the disturbance: (a) RSC/E-STATCOM, (b) equivalent SPGM, and (c) PPM.

Fig. 12. Reactive power response of the RSC/E-STATCOM (a), and voltage evolution at the NCP (b), following the disturbance.

Fig. 13. Reactive power response of the equivalent SPGM (a) and the GFL PPM (b) following the disturbance.

Fig. 14. PPM node voltage, v_{PPM} .

5.3. Voltage control

Fig. 8 (c) illustrates the schematic representation for this set of simulations, conducted to demonstrate that the incorporation of the E-STATCOM enables effective voltage control at the NCP. To achieve this, the E-STATCOM incorporates a voltage control loop to ensure that the GFM converter maintains the RMS voltage at the NCP at 1 p.u.

Following an initial electrical state similar to that of the previous simulations—where the GFM converter adjusts its reactive power output to maintain this voltage—the disturbance occurs at $t = 5$ s. This disturbance corresponds to the connection of an additional load at the NCP, increasing reactive power demand at the node, with $P_2 = 0$ MW and $Q_2 = 15$ MVar.

Fig. 12(a) shows the reactive power response of the RSC and the E-STATCOM following the disturbance, while Fig. 12(b) shows the voltage

evolution at the NCP.

For this case, the responses for the two PSS parameterizations are highly similar. The scenarios that include either the RSC or the E-STATCOM enable more effective voltage control at the NCP following the disturbance, due to the adjustment of their reactive power injection. Moreover, when the E-STATCOM regulates voltage at the node, the voltage profile exhibits fewer oscillations.

In scenario 1), which includes only the GFL PPM, the equivalent SPGM is responsible for compensating the additional load, as illustrated in Fig. 13(a), while also regulating the voltage at its terminals. This, in combination with the behavior of the GFL PGM—which simply maintains its reactive power setpoint, as shown in Fig. 13(b)—leads to a greater voltage deviation.

Fig. 15. Detail of the current injected by the RSC and the E-STATCOM (a), shown in kA, and q-axis current component of the E-STATCOM (b), shown in p.u.

5.4. Fault response

Fig. 8(d) presents the schematic representation for the simulations conducted to assess the system response to a fault. The initial electrical state is identical to that in previous simulations. At $t = 5$ s, a balanced three-phase fault occurs at the PPM node, with a duration of 500 ms and fault inductance of 0.001 H. This fault event causes a voltage dip of 0.8 p.u., as shown in Fig. 14, which presents the voltage evolution at this node.

For this simulation, only the results for the first set of PSS parameters are represented. Fig. 15(a) provides a detailed view of the current injected by the RCS and the E-STATCOM cases during and after the voltage dip (note the difference in scale on the vertical axis, expressed in kA). As can be seen, the E-STATCOM meets the requirements for continuity of supply under voltage dips.

The short-circuit current of the RSC shows asymmetrical variations with respect to the horizontal axis due to the appearance of transient or DC currents, considering the differences between the three phases of the synchronous machine at the moment the fault occurs. The peak instantaneous current for the RSC reaches 4.445 kA. However, the E-STATCOM current does not exhibit such asymmetries and, due to the current limitation, the peak current reaches only 1.688 kA, with both configurations having the same nominal current. Contrary to the natural response provided by the RSC, the short-circuit current limitation by control of the E-STATCOM is a favorable characteristic to address the problem of exceeding the permissible short-circuit current limits, as identified by the Spanish TSO for certain nodes.

Fig. 15(b) shows the q -axis current injected by the E-STATCOM during the voltage dip. This response is presented in p.u. in order to verify that the converter behaves as expected by injecting current up to its rated capacity, typically prioritizing reactive current to support voltage restoration. As observed, during the disturbance, the q -axis current reaches values close to 1 p.u., providing reactive support to the

grid and contributing to voltage recovery. This response highlights the capability of the E-STATCOM to meet LVRT requirements by injecting reactive current.

6. Conclusions

This paper proposes the use of E-STATCOMs, consisting of an energy storage system interfaced with a GFM converter, as a viable and more flexible alternative to rotating synchronous condensers for increasing the grid access capacity in power systems with high penetration of non-synchronous renewable generation. E-STATCOMs can effectively support grid strength by providing equivalent functionalities in terms of voltage support, inertial response, and power oscillation damping, while also complying with LVRT requirements. They overcome challenges related to exceeding maximum permissible short-circuit current levels and subsynchronous torsional interactions, issues that have led the Spanish TSO to explicitly limit the deployment of RSCs for grid access capacity enhancement. Furthermore, they offer more flexibility by enabling adjustments to their dynamic response through control approaches.

A control strategy based on the synchronous machine swing equation emulation, combined with a power system stabilizer, has been proposed to ensure stable dynamic system response while maintaining the behavior of RSCs in steady state.

PSCAD simulations validate the approach by demonstrating improved frequency nadir, reduced *RoCoF*, enhanced voltage control in weak grids, and compliance with FRT requirements. The results support grid-forming E-STATCOMs as suitable devices for increasing system strength, thereby facilitating higher integration of renewable energy.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Carolina M. Martín: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Santiago Arnaltes:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Francisco Arredondo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jaime Alonso-Martínez:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **José Luis Rodríguez-Amenedo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A

Simulation parameters

Table A.1
Global system parameters

Parameter	Value	Units
Base voltage at PCC node	220	kV
Base voltage at EQ_{SYSTEM} node	220	kV
Base voltage at GEN_{EQ} node	20	kV
Base voltage at PPM node	20	kV
Base voltage at SC node	20	kV
System base power	500	MVA

Values calculated according to the methodology described in the Technical Standard [30].

Table A.2
GFL converter parameters

Parameter	Value	Units
Rated apparent power S_n, GFL	100	MVA
Rated line-to-line voltage (RMS) $V_{LL, GFL}^{rated}$	20	kV
Series impedance of the output filter Z_s, GFL	0.2	p.u. GFL base
X/R ratio	60	s
Filter capacitance C_f, GFL	0.1	p.u. GFL base
Switching frequency $f_{sw, GFL}$	3	kHz

Values calculated based on design specifications and following the procedure described in [24].

Table A.3
GFM converter parameters

Parameter	Value	Units
Rated apparent power S_n, GFM	30	MVA
Rated line-to-line voltage (RMS) $V_{LL, GFM}^{rated}$	20	kV
Series impedance of the output filter Z_s, GFM	0.2	p.u. GFM base
X/R ratio	60	s
Filter capacitance C_f, GFM	0.1	p.u. GFM base
Switching frequency $f_{sw, GFM}$	3	kHz
Inertia constant APC loop H	6.25	s
Damping coefficient APC loop D	0	
PSS₁ parameters		
PSS gain constant T_{w1}	1.2	s
PSS gain constant K_{w1}	0.01	
PSS₂ parameters		
PSS gain constant T_{w2}	1.2	s
PSS gain constant K_{w2}	0.05	

Values calculated based on design specifications and following the procedure described in [24].

Table A.4
Rotative synchronous condenser parameters

Parameter	Value	Units
Rated apparent power S_n, RSC	30	MVA
Transient time constant to direct axis open circuit T'_{do}	4.61	s
Sub-transient time constant to direct axis open circuit T''_{do}	0.054	s
Transient time constant to open circuit quadrature axis T'_{qo}	1.5	s
Sub-transient time constant to open-circuit quadrature axis T''_{qo}	0.107	s
Armature resistance R_a	0.004	p.u. RSC base
Direct axis synchronous reactance X_d	1.85	p.u. RSC base
Quadrature axis synchronous reactance X_q	1.74	p.u. RSC base
Direct axis transient reactance X'_d	0.225	p.u. RSC base
Quadrature axis transient reactance X'_q	0.306	p.u. RSC base
Direct and Quadrature axis sub-transient reactance $X''_d = X''_q$	0.2	p.u. RSC base
Leakage reactance X_l	0.113	p.u. RSC base
Inertia Constant H	6.25	s (nominal S base)

Parameters for the RCS correspond to the synchronous machine described in the Technical Standard [30].

Table A.5
Equivalent synchronous generator parameters GEN_{EQ}

Parameter	Value	Units
Maximum apparent power S_{GENEQ}	500	MVA
Transient time constant to direct axis open circuit T'_{do}	4.61	s
Sub-transient time constant to direct axis open circuit T''_{do}	0.054	s
Transient time constant to open circuit quadrature axis T'_{qo}	1.5	s
Sub-transient time constant to open-circuit quadrature axis T''_{qo}	0.107	s
Armature resistance R_d	0	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base
Direct axis synchronous reactance X_d	1.85	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base
Quadrature axis synchronous reactance X_q	1.74	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base
Direct axis transient reactance X'_d	0.225	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base
Quadrature axis transient reactance X'_q	0.306	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base
Direct and quadrature axis sub-transient reactance $X''_d = X''_q$	0.2	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base
Leakage reactance X_l	0.113	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base
Inertia Constant H	2.5	s (nominal S base)

Parameters for the equivalent SPGM (GEN_{EQ}) are provided in the Technical Standard [30].

Table A.6
Lines and transformers parameters.

Parameter	Value	Units
TRF_{EQ} rated apparent power $S_{n,TRFEQ}$	500	MVA
TRF_{EQ} rated voltages HV/LV	220/20	kV
TRF_{EQ} short-circuit impedance $Z_{cc,TRFEQ}$	0.12	p.u. base TRF_{EQ}
TRF_{GFL} rated apparent power $S_{n,TRFGFL}$	100	MVA
TRF_{GFL} rated voltages HV/LV	220/20	kV
TRF_{GFL} short-circuit impedance $Z_{cc,TRFGFL}$	0.1	p.u. base TRF_{GFL}
TRF_{GFM} rated apparent power $S_{n,TRFGFM}$	30	MVA
TRF_{GFM} rated voltages HV/LV	220/20	kV
TRF_{GFM} short-circuit impedance $Z_{cc,TRFGFM}$	0.1	p.u. base TRF_{GFM}
Line $EQ_{SYSTEM-NCP}$ reactance X	0.6709	p.u. system base
Line $EQ_{SYSTEM-NCP}$ resistance R	0.1342	p.u. system base

Values calculated according to the methodology described in the Technical Standard [30].

Table A.7
 GEN_{EQ} excitation system voltage regulator parameters (SEXS type).

Parameter	Value	Units
Excitation regulator time constant T_E	0.1	s
Excitation regulator gain K	100	
Lower limit of excitation voltage E_{min}	0	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base
Upper limit of excitation voltage E_{max}	5	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base
Advance-delay network lead time constant T_A	1	s
Advance-delay network lead time constant T_B	10	s

Parameters for the equivalent SPGM (GEN_{EQ}) are provided in the Technical Standard [30].

Table A.8
 GEN_{EQ} speed regulation system parameters (TGOV1 type)

Parameter	Value	Units
Regulator droop R	0.05	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base
Regulator time constant T_1	0.5	s
Maximum valve aperture V_{max}	1	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base
Minimum valve aperture V_{min}	0.15	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base
Time constant T_2 (T_2/T_3 : high pressure fraction)	3	s
Overheating time constant T_3	10	s
Turbine damping D_t	0	p.u. GEN_{EQ} base

Parameters for the equivalent SPGM (GEN_{EQ}) are provided in the Technical Standard [30].

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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